

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

Rawls and Walzer on Justice: Relevance of their Ideas for Contemporary Democratic Systems

Paper Id : 20222 Submission Date : 2025-05-03 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-18 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15807215

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Rahul Chaudhary

Assistant Professor
Political Science
University Of Rajasthan
Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Abstract

Justice is regarded as the most important political value, as legitimacy of a political system depends on its efficiency to deliver justice to its citizens. Democracy is now considered as the best form of government but in the contemporary times, these democratic systems are facing certain challenges, in the social sphere- fragmented social structure, in the economic field- rising inequality between the rich and the poor and in the political sphere- corruption, loss of individual freedom etc. The present study seeks to understand and analyse these challenges from the theoretical framework.

In the contemporary political theory, Rawls propounded a significant liberal theory of justice, which includes, within its scope, two other important political values- liberty and equality. Similarly, Walzer offered an alternative to Rawls theory of justice, in the form of his communitarian theory of justice. A comparative and empirical investigation of both the theories of justice is done in the current paper. Also, through this examination an attempt will be made to access the relevance of these theories in resolving the challenges faced by the modern democratic systems

Keywords John Rawls, Michael Walzer, Justice, Political Theory, Liberty, Equality

Introduction

From the ancient to modern times, Justice has occupied a central place in the realm of political theory. Several thinkers from Plato to Rawls or Walzer have regarded justice as most vital political value, which is essential for the establishment of a strong and stable political system. Justice is also important because it synthesises or reconnects other political values like liberty, equality, rights etc. to create a just environment for the citizens (Barker, 1951). Justice demands that, within a social system, balance between these political values can only ensure optimum conditions for the fullest development of the individual as well as the society.

However, though justice is a significant political value but its precise definition could not be offered. Several political theorists have given different definitions of justice and on that basis certain conclusions, regarding the meaning of justice can be deduced. Firstly, justice stresses upon both liberty and equality in the society, so that different social structure could be function smoothly. Secondly, justice is related to the scientific temper and common sense or wisdom of the society. Finally, justice demands that the resources or values in the society should be distributed on rational basis.

As far as the democratic systems are concerned, they are based on the will of the people and they have to rule according to the common interest rather than confining themselves to the interest of any particular group (Finer, 1970). So, it becomes important for these structures to ensure justice to their citizens. For this, theoretically, the contemporary democratic systems have to supplement the liberty of the individual with the concept of social equality, so that the aims of the 'responsive state' could be achieved. Practically, the political system has to ensure that its different structures like executive, legislature, judiciary etc. and the other social structure including press, NGOs etc. functions independently and for the welfare of the whole society.

Objective of study

The present paper seeks to analyse the two contemporary theories of justice, one, that is, Rawls advocated the liberal notion of justice, while the other, Walzer established the communitarian concept of justice. The article also makes a comparative study of the theories of both the philosophers and tries to discover the similarities as well as dissimilarities between their ideas on justice. It also makes empirical observation about the state of representative institutions in the contemporary democratic structure. The innovate aspect of the paper is that, it tries to apply the conception of justice of these two thinkers in presenting theoretical solution to the problems faced by the democratic systems of the world in recent times

Review of Literature

Rawls J. (1971) is a classical work, which puts forward a liberal theory of justice. In this book, Rawls propounded his two principles of justice, which he believes will ensure justice to every member of the society. Rawls, a supporter of deliberative democracy, argues that both political values, liberty and equality, are essential for establishing justice. **Walzer, M. (1983)** has presented a communitarian alternative to Rawls' theory of justice. The author believes that there cannot be universal conception of justice, rather any notion of the justice has to be essentially community specific. Through his conception of complex equality, Walzer has tried to establish principles of justice in various spheres of the life. **Mulhall, S. and Swift, A. (1992)** has made a comparative analysis of the liberal and communitarian perspectives. The authors have discussed and analysed in detail the theories of several contemporary liberal and communitarian thinkers including Rawls and Walzer. They have pointed out the shortcomings of the liberal notion and how communitarian perspective is different from it. **Levitsky, S. & Ziblatt, D. (2019)** have discussed in details the reasons for the recent decline in democracy around the globe. They have pointed out several historical explanations to understand the current slide in democratic values. They have also made suggestion to restrengthen democratic institution for the benefit of society and individuals. **Dahl, R. (2001)** is a standard work on democracy. It discusses that how democracy have survived over other forms of government. The author discusses the real meaning and nature of democracy and its essentiality for the human beings. The book also analysis the challenges before the democratic regimes and how they can be dealt with.

Main Text

Rawls theory of Justice:

Rawls regards that justice is the first virtue of all socio-political institutions. It means that the aim of every institution is to function in a justful manner. It can also be deduced from this, that individuals should establish fair institutions and just procedures should be adopted in them. Rawls believes that, if the basic institutions of the society functions according to the declared fair principles, then they will be able to distribute the benefits and burdens of the society in a just and rational manner (Rawls, 1971). Rawls is concerned with devising such 'principles', through which the basic or primary goods of the society could be distributed in a way, which ensure justice to all its members. Here,

the term basic or primary goods includes all essential commodities or values which an individual desires for the fullest development of its personality.

For developing these just principles, Rawls adopts a methodology which, according to him, should also be fair and neutral. So, he starts with an 'original position'. It is a hypothetical condition of human existence in which the people who wants to establish fair institutions come together to discover just principles of justice. Rawls further states that, in this situation these people are under the 'veil of ignorance'. This term veil of ignorance means that the contractors, who have come together to formulate the principles of justice in original position, will not have any information about their future condition or position in the society. In such situation, these contractors will not be guided by any class, caste or race considerations. In this way, Rawls have made the contractors free from all prejudices, so that they can formulate fair principles of justice.

Rawls describes his conception of justice as 'justice as fairness' and differentiates it from the 'utilitarian principle', which he does not regard as a moral principle of justice. In fact, Rawls criticises the utilitarian principle of justice and therefore tries to provide an alternative to it through his theory of justice. The 'justice as fairness' supports a well-ordered society, based on reciprocal benefit of all the individuals, regulated by the principles agreed upon by the individuals themselves. On the other hand, the utilitarianism views society as a system, which performs the function of efficient management of resources, to satisfy the desires of the maximum numbers, constructed by a neutral spectator (Sandel, 1984). Rawls theory of justice is also different from the traditional social contractualist theory. The contractualists tried to explain the origin of the state through their notion of 'state of nature' and 'social contract', whereas Rawls through his notion of 'original position' and 'veil of ignorance' tries to discover fair principles of justice, which will help to establish a just state.

According to Rawls, the contractors in the original position, under the veil of ignorance, will choose the principles of justice among several alternatives available to them. Through the method of 'reflective equilibrium' these contractors will agree upon two principles of justice, which are-

1. 'Each individual should have an equal right to the most wide-ranging system of basic liberties, which is compatible with similar set of liberty for all the individuals.'

2. 'Socio-economic inequalities are to be arranged in such a manner, so that they are both'-

(a) 'Rationally accepted to be beneficial for everyone's advantage', and

(b) 'Attached to the positions and offices open to all, under the state of equality of opportunity.' (Rawls, 1971)

The first principle has been described as the 'principle of equality of liberty', while the 2 (a) is called as the 'difference principle' and the 2(b) is known as the 'principle of equality of opportunity'. Rawls has also given a 'lexical order' to these principles of justice. For him, in case of conflict, the first principle should always get priority over the second principle. Likewise, he gives priority to principle of equality of opportunity over the principle of difference.

Basic Structures and a Just Social Order:

Rawls formulated these principles of justice to regulate the basic structures of the society. According to him, a just society could be established only when its basic structures, which includes all the significant socio-economic, political, legal and other institutions, functions in a fair manner, limited by just principles. After the formulation of the principles of justice, the people will formulate the constitution. A constitution is a document where preference will be given to the principle of liberty, that is, it will safeguard the liberties of the citizens and hence Rawls becomes a supporter of constitutional democracy, as the government powers will be bound by the constitution.

The second principle comes into force at the stage of legislation. At this stage, the legislature should have knowledge about the socio-economic condition of the citizens, so that it can make laws for the benefit of the least advantaged sections of the society. But, while doing so, it should not violate the principle of liberty and the principle of equality of opportunity. Rawls argues that unless the basic structures functions for the upliftment of the weaker sections of the society, all the individuals could not enjoy the benefits of the other principles of justice, and this would itself be a violation of the notion of justice.

Hence, using the 'analogy of chain', he puts forward the argument, that for establishing a healthy and strong society, it is essential that the least advantaged sections of the society should be strengthened.

Thus, Rawls believes that the basic structures of the society should- ensure equal liberty to all the individuals, promote equality of opportunity and make laws for the upliftment of the weaker sections of the society. These structures are bound by the constitutional obligations and has to operate according to the principles of justice. Rawls also points out that the individuals should also perform their duties, so that these basic structures could function properly. In this way, the basic structures and individuals together, through the fulfilment of their respective obligations, contribute towards the establishment of a just social order.

Walzer's theory of Justice:

Michael Walzer has presented a communitarian theory of justice in his book 'Spheres of Justice'. He rejects the attempts to present universal accounts of justice, rather believes that any functional theory of justice has to be essentially local in nature (Walzer, 1983). Several theorists have tried to develop general theory of justice, in the recent times, but they are more philosophical in nature, whereas the communitarian theory of justice of Walzer is more acceptable to the people as it is pluralistic in nature and flexible enough to take into account the local values and norms (Hartogh, 1999).

Walzer starts with his theory of 'Social Goods', which occupies central place in his distributive model of justice. According to him, there are plurality of goods available for distribution in the society (which he describes as social goods), and hence there cannot be a single distributive principle of justice. The meaning and value of these goods are determined by the society; hence different goods have different values in diverse societies. So, there should be different principles of justice for the distribution of these goods. According to Walzer, the social meaning, that is, shared understanding of society members about the good's nature, importance and relevance, regulates the process for its distribution. Also, every 'social good' has its own sphere and once its 'social meaning' is determined, then accordingly its distributive principle should be settled by the members of the society. Thus, there can be many spheres in the society and correspondingly, there exists plurality of distributive principles.

Moving ahead, Walzer in order to explain his theory of complex equality, differentiates between 'Dominance' and 'Monopoly'. According to Walzer, there are different spheres in the society and in each sphere, there is a significant good for which the individuals compete with each other. For example, money is an important good in the economic sphere or power is a vital good in the political sphere etc. The people try to control the significant good of a particular sphere, and it has been described as 'Monopoly' by the Walzer. On the other hand, when the same people use their monopoly, over a good in one sphere, to achieve the vital good of other sphere, that is, when these people, through their monopoly in one sphere influences the distribution of vital good of other sphere, then it has been described by Walzer as 'Dominance'. Walzer believes that 'monopoly' as such is not harmful, because within a sphere different individuals compete and those who are capable controls the vital good of that sphere. Also, there is possibility of change among those people (circulation of elites), who controls the vital good because there is continuous competition. According to him, it is the 'dominance' which has to be eliminated because it enables the people to unduly control the significant good of different spheres and thereby kills the free competition existing in different spheres. Walzer holds that different ideologies demand eradication of monopoly, whereas the real problem exists in dominance, which could be resolved through his theory of complex equality.

Simple Equality and Complex Equality:

According to Walzer, an important component of justice is equality. But, here Walzer distinguishes between 'simple equality' and 'complex equality'. He states that the supporters of simple equality demand equal distribution of the vital good of a sphere among all the individuals, that is, they are against monopoly. Simple equality stresses on equal enjoyment and ownership of some good by all (Miller, 1995). Walzer points out that the system of simple equality cannot be sustained for long as individuals have different capacities and they will use the vital good according to it, so inequalities will again creep into the society. Therefore, Walzer claims that the purpose of any notion of distributive justice should be to establish complex equality. Here, complex equality means that different individuals should be able to monopolies the vital goods of different spheres, so a system of complex equality, among individuals, will be established in the society. In other words, there are several spheres in every society and each sphere has a vital good. The value or relevance of that good is determined by its social meaning. This social meaning also determines the method of its distribution among the individuals. This is decided with respect to all the spheres. Now, in all the spheres, the individuals are free to compete with each other to attain the vital goods, according to their capacities. Thus,

different individuals will be able to achieve different vital goods in diverse spheres and thereby complex equality will be established in the society. Here, it is important to point out that, in this system, the individuals who monopolises one vital good, of a specific sphere, will not be allowed to extend their monopoly to other sphere, that is, on the basis of attainment of one vital good, they cannot influence the distribution of vital good of another sphere.

On the basis of above analysis, the main features of 'Walzer's theory of justice' are-

1) The society should be pluralistic in nature. That is, there should be large number of spheres in the society each having its own vital element. These spheres should command equality of status and they should be open for all the individuals.

2) The society determines the social meaning of these vital goods and on that basis decides the distributive principles, within each sphere. Then the individuals are free to compete in these spheres according to their merit.

3) The individuals can attain vital good of a sphere, but they cannot use that good for the attainment of other vital goods belonging to other spheres. Thus, the autonomy of each sphere should be protected. The different sphere should function independently, without interference by another sphere. The notion of complex equality is based on the art of separation and protecting the boundaries of each sphere (Walzer, 1984).

4) It is the responsibility of the state to ensure that the vital element or good of a particular sphere is not violating the distributive principle of another sphere. The state should respect the local norms and represent the will of the people. Thus, Walzer supports a decentralized democratic socialist state.

Rawls and Walzer: A Comparative Analysis

Rawls and Walzer presents two ideologically diverse theories of justice. Rawls presents libertarian theory of justice, whereas Walzer's theory can be described as communitarian in nature. Rawls, in his theory of justice gives importance to the liberty of the individual, whereas for Walzer the principles of distributive justice are to be determined according to the norms or values of the community. As a result, Rawls has been described as libertarian philosopher, whereas Walzer is placed in the category of communitarian thinkers.

Rawls, as a liberal thinker, has tried to develop a universal theory of justice, which it is believed can be applied to any political system. On the other hand, Walzer states that there cannot be a universal or general theory of justice. Every theory of justice has to take into account, the will of the community. Hence, Walzer tried to develop his theory taking into account the cultural diversities of various communities. Further, Rawls starts with a hypothetical situation described as the 'original position' and on its basis develops his theory of justice. This has been criticised by the communitarians because the theories of justice cannot be developed in vacuum, rather they are community specific.

Again, Rawls develops a single list of primary goods and applies it on all the societies, irrespective of their cultural diversities. While, Walzer states that in every society there can be different sets social goods, whose value and relevance, that is, 'social meaning' is determined by the community itself. As Rawls draws a single list of primary goods, so he has developed general principles of distributive justice, which are applicable on all goods, in all societies. Whereas, according to Walzer, the social meaning of every good is different in diverse societies, so on its basis the principles of distributive justice, in various societies, are also different for all the spheres.

Rawls, in his theory have explicitly dealt with the notion of social justice, by stating that the state should work for the least advantaged section of the society. Though, Walzer has not directly discussed about the backward sections of the society but he too believes that the state should be socialist in nature. Walzer points out that there should not be excessive gap between the rich and the poor, as it will be against the stability of the community. Also, Rawls gives more importance to the procedures and focusses only on the basic structures of the society. But, for Walzer the social meaning of the goods is more relevant and he stresses on various spheres of the society.

Though, Rawls and Walzer represents two different sets of ideologies, yet on serious analysis, it can be observed that there exists certain convergence in their ideas. Firstly, Walzer in his theory of justice emphasises on the separation and autonomy of various spheres. This separation of spheres, such as political and economic sphere, is the basic characteristics of the liberal philosophy. Again, Walzer stresses on tolerance and respect

for all cultures and communities. This is also regarded as an important aspect of the liberal ideology (Mulhall & Swift, 1992).

An important aspect of the theories of justice of both, Rawls and Walzer, is that they have tried to create a balance between liberty and equality. It means that both believes that if justice has to be established in the society, then a synthesis between liberty and equality has to be secured. Further, as a liberal philosopher, Rawls has emphasised on the liberty and merit of the individual in his theory of justice. Walzer, while giving importance to community-based principles of justice, has ensured that once the values of justice are determined then, within the sphere the individual is free to act according to its merit. Thus, Walzer also supports individual liberty and merit within the sphere.

Again, both the converge on the issue of nature of the state. Rawls supports a democratic state based on the notion of constitutionalism. As a liberal thinker, he believes that the state should be pluralistic and decentralized in its form. The state should work for the betterment of the least advantaged section of the society; this gives a socialistic aspect to Rawlsian state. Likewise, Walzer has clearly stated that, to achieve communitarian justice, the state should be decentralized democratic socialist in its nature.

The theories of justice of Rawls and Walzer is different from the utilitarian theory of justice on the ground that, while utilitarian theory focuses on justice to greatest number, the theories of justice of both Rawls and Walzer seeks to ensure justice to every member of the society. Also, another similarity between Rawls and Walzer is that for establishing a just society, the basic institution should be strengthened. Rawls points out that, the basic institution should function according to the principles of justice and should be bound by the values of the constitution. Similarly, Walzer also states that the various structures of the society should work independently, without any interference by external factors.

Relevance of Rawls and Walzer for Contemporary Democratic Systems:

The disintegration of the USSR and with it the collapse of communist ideology led to the success of the liberal ideology (Fukuyama, 1992). With this, the democracy became the most established and popular form of government, as it is based on the consent of the people and hence has no alternate of its own (Arblaster, 1997). However, in the recent past various international indices, like 'The Democracy Index' by Economist Intelligence Unit, 'The Democracy Report' by V-Dem Institute, 'Global State of Democracy Initiative' by International IDEA and 'Freedom in the World Report' by Freedom House, points out that there has been a global decline in the status of democracy across the world. This decline in the democratic values and practices has been attributed to several factors, but in the current paper few fundamental issues of every sphere- Social, Economic and Political has been dealt with keeping in view the scope of the paper.

As far as the social sphere is concerned, the failure of the liberal politics to deliver its promise of upliftment of all the sections of the society, through the process of liberalization, globalisation and privatisation has led to the disillusionment among the people towards the liberal political parties (Sandel, 2020). The widening economic gap between the beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries led to fragmentation among the members of the society, and hence the group interests became more important than the common interest, also deep polarisation can be witnessed in the society, which is harmful for participatory democracy. Further, the rise of populism and politics based on the interest of the majority created rifts in the social structure and as a result, the notion of multiculturalism received serious challenge from the populist supporters. All this has raised serious concerns about one of the fundamental features of liberal democracy, that is, pluralism.

At the theoretical level, through the synthesis of the 'chain principle' of Rawls and emphasis on 'community spirit' as advocated by Walzer, could provide an answer to this social discontent. Rawls through his chain principle has encouraged the basic institutions of the society to work for social justice, that is, emphasis should be given on strengthening the position of the least advantaged sections of the society. Walzer has also pointed out that in the age of neo-capitalism the individual should not be regarded as atomistic in nature, rather the community spirit of the individual should be highlighted. When the needs of all the members of the society are satisfied or represented through proper channels, then the fear or mistrust towards other groups can be eliminated, leading to the advancement of pluralism in the society.

Again, economic inequality, which is rising in different countries of the world, has also threatened the functioning of the democratic institutions (Stiglitz, 2023).

According to several reports the top one percent of the world elites controls more wealth than ninety-five percent of the population of the world. This unequal distribution of wealth has led to an increase in the capacity of the capitalists to control the political structures as well. The erosion of the boundaries between the economic and political sphere, has led to the reduction in the legitimacy of the political structures among majority of the poor people. The economic discriminatory situations have led to a decline of established liberal values in the society.

Rawls and Walzer, both have propounded the distributive theories of justice, which seeks to ensure proper dispersal of resources in the society. They have tried to establish a balance between the market economy and the notion of welfare state, which is essential for securing justice to every individual in the society. Rawls supports liberty to the individual and autonomous functioning of the economic sphere, but at the same time, stresses that for proper enjoyment of liberty and implementation of the principle of equality of opportunity, minimum level playing field should be guaranteed to the weaker sections of the society, by the state. Similarly, Walzer points out that once the norms of justice are established in economic sphere according to the will of the community, then the individual is free to exercise his rational choice and also the state should try to satisfy, through community-based programmes, the needs of the backward sections of the society. In this way, both philosophers have pointed out that, through conscious efforts by the political structures, the gap between the rich and the poor should be reduced, for strengthening the democratic values in the society. Further, both the thinkers have highlighted a significant aspect, that justice could be established in the society only when the basic structures of the society function, according to constitutionalism, in an independent manner and on the basis of the will of all and not for few rich people.

The political structure is the explicit aspect of democratic norms in all the nations of the world. Though, these structures appear to be representative in nature, but in reality, during the last few years, there has been a decline in the democratic values due to corruption- increasing economic control over political system, loss of liberties and extreme ideological polarity. The people in power are filling their own pockets (O' Neil, 2020) and clientelism is on the rise, though it has its own limitations. The political institutions are drifting away from the established liberal feature of constitutional integrity, protection of civil liberties and acceptance of diversity. In such conditions, serious questions have been raised over the democratic character of these institutions.

Rawls and Walzer have pointed out that the economic and political power should be separated. According to Rawls, through constitutional institutions of the integrity of the political system should be safeguarded. Likewise, Walzer also emphasised on the need that economic benefits should not be used to attain political power. This can be done by protecting the boundaries of political sphere, through implementation of the principles of 'complex equality'. If the margins of the economic and political spheres are kept intact, then the challenge of corruption can be dealt with in the democratic regimes. Again, Rawls support deliberative form of democracy, which encourages decisions through deliberations among all the members of the society. Walzer also desires that for healthy society, the diverse cultures and values should be respected and protected. This will ensure that the liberties of all the members are protected and instead of ideological polarity, a convergence or common will is created which takes into account the welfare of all the sections of the society. This will provide true democratic nature to the political institutions.

Methodology

The present paper uses analytical and descriptive means to understand the liberal and communitarian theories of justice. The paper tries to discover, through comparative and diagnostic methodology, the common and different perspectives in the ideas of Rawls and Walzer. With the help of empirical and scientific approach the paper discusses about the contemporary challenges, that have led to the decline of democratic values in the world. Finally, through innovate, rational and critical observation the paper puts forward the relevance of these two theories of justice.

Conclusion

Thus, on the basis of above analysis it can be concluded that though, Rawls and Walzer represents two diverse perspectives on justice, the former embodies the liberal aspect whereas the latter expresses views encouraging communitarian facet, yet there are certain points on which they converge, like both favour liberty of the individual, supports measures for the establishment of social justice, separation of various spheres, respect for divergent ideologies etc. Further, as there is a decline in the democratic practices and institutional values in the recent times. In such situation, on theoretical ground, a synthesis of their views can be helpful for strengthening the democratic institutions. Few significant observations that can be drawn from their ideas, which will greatly help in this regard, are- for ensuring complete justice in the society, a fusion of liberty and equality is essential, and for the welfare of all the sections of the society, emphasis should be given on both, free market and welfare state

References

1. Arblaster, A. (1997). *Democracy*. New Delhi: Viva Books.
2. Barker, E. (1951). *Principles of Social and Political Theory*. London: Oxford University Press.
3. Dahl, R. (2001). *On Democracy*. New Delhi: East West Press Eds.
4. Finer, S.E. (1970). *Comparative Government*. London: Penguin Press.
5. Fukuyama, F. (1992). *The End of the History and the Last Man*. UK: Penguin.
6. Hartogh, G. D. (1999). *The Architectonic of Michael Walzer's Theory of Justice*. *Political Theory*; 27(4) pp. 491-522.
7. Heywood, A. (2022). *Political Theory: An Introduction*. London: Bloomsbury.
8. Levitsky, S. & Ziblatt, D. (2019). *How Democracies Die: What History Reveals About Our Futures*. UK: Penguin.
9. Miller, D. (1995). *Complex Equality* in Miller, D. & Walzer, M. (Eds.). *Pluralism, Justice and Equality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
10. Mulhall, S. and Swift, A. (1992). *Liberals and Communitarians*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
11. O'Neil, Patrick. (2020). *Essentials of Comparative Politics (7th ed.)*. New York: W. W. Norton & Co Inc.
12. Rawls, J. (1971). *A Theory of Justice*. Harvard: Harvard University Press.
13. Sandel, M. (Ed.) (1984). *Liberalism and its Critics*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
14. Sandel, M. (2020). *The Tyranny of Merit: What's Become of the Common Good?* UK: Penguin Random House.
15. Stiglitz, J. (2023). *Inequality and Democracy*. Project Syndicate cited from <https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/inequality-source-of-lost-confidence-in-liberal-democracy-by-joseph-e-stiglitz-2023> on 20/05/2025.
16. Walzer, M. (1983). *Spheres of Justice: A Defence of Pluralism and Equality*. Oxford: Robertson & Company Ltd.
17. Walzer, M. (1984). *Liberalism and the Art of Separation*. *Political Theory* 12 (August). pp. 315-330